

INFLUENCE OF FAMILY ENVIRONMENT ON MENTAL HEALTH OF POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS

P. Santhi

Ph.D. Scholar, Osmania University, India

Dr. Saroj Arya

Former Associate Professor & HOD in Rehabilitation Psychology,
NIEPID Secunderabad, India;

Professor Emeritus in Clinical Psychology, Sweekar Academy of Rehabilitation Sciences,
Secunderabad, India

ABSTRACT

The family environment plays a crucial role in shaping the psychological well-being and mental health of college students, especially among post graduate students. . Positive family dynamics, such as cohesion, open communication, and emotional support, can contribute to better mental health outcomes, while negative dynamics, such as conflict, neglect, and lack of support, can lead to psychological disturbances such as anxiety, depression, and stress. Understanding and addressing these factors it is found essential to study the influence of family environment on the mental health status of postgraduate students. With this objective a study has been conducted on the postgraduate students studying in colleges and universities of Hyderabad city with the help of research tools namely, Family Environment scale and Mental Health inventory. In addition, the demographic questionnaire was developed to gather the data of post graduate students. The data was collected from the selected 60 respondents who are studying post-graduation in Arts, Science, Commerce and Management courses. The data was analysed with suitable statistics and the results of the study revealed that there is a positive association found between good family environment and low scores on stress, anxiety and depression of postgraduate students. Therefore, it could be concluded that enhancing positive family relationships may improve student mental health. Dysfunctional families relate to poorer adjustment. Hence, fostering healthy family environments could have enduring benefits for postgraduate students' psychological well-being, which reflects on their mental health.

Keywords: Family Environment, Mental Health.

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INTRODUCTION

Family is an eternal school of life. A child sees the light of the day in the home. Family is the first social environment where he fulfills his physical, mental and cultural needs. Family environment is the nucleus of all other social institutions. Family interaction plays an important role in the development of an individual. The healthy functioning of these interaction patterns enhances mental health (Kour, et al., 2015). There are some important interactional effects between family and its members at differential stages. It influences the whole life of the children, especially adolescents who are studying post graduation. A clear understanding of roles in the context of family function is very important in shaping the future of postgraduates. In college days, the friends and peers group have great pressure on various decisions of adolescents, but literature clearly shows the continued importance of parents in shaping the behaviors and choices of adolescents as they face the challenges of growing up. Positive parents-children relationship, good parenting skills, shared family responsibilities, and optimistic parent role modeling all have effects on adolescents' health, growth, and development. These are the areas where the parent can make choices to make positive changes for their children (Aufseeser, et al., 2006). Researchers have consistently proved that both overall family system functioning and parental behavior are positively related to adolescence. Thus we can say that family environment moulds the behavior, personality, aptitude and self-esteem of the adolescents, especially the youth in the age group of 15-20 years. Therefore, the family environment plays a decisive role in the quality of peer interaction among young students; for example, parents supervise their children's home time, places to go out, friend interactions, and academic performance, which would increase students' exposure to peers with positive learning behaviors (DeAnna, 2016), which indicates that parent-child communication and parental educational involvement influence students' interpersonal interactions. At the same time, the peer network structure, friend quality, and personality orientation also affect students' academic achievement (Golsteyn et al., 2021). Based on the available research, a more superior family environment may have a positive effect not only on students' academic achievement by increasing their peer interaction quality, but also on their mental health. Thus, a brief discussion on the family environment and mental health are presented.

FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

Family is the most important system for a child which fosters the growth and development of human being. In this regard Ozcinar (2006) opined family is a primary socialization context and considered as an important factor influencing child development. Vanwell (2000) also emphasized that family members are very important factors influencing survival, thus, strong emotional bonds evolved to foster long term commitment among parents, children and relatives. Therefore, family cohesion and supportive relationships between family members are associated with psychological adaptations of children, especially in their youth (Herman et al. 2007). The conducive family environment could contribute to a healthy personality development. Brenoe and Lundberg (2018) ascertained that boys were benefited more from an advantageous family environment than do girls in terms of grade-school outcomes and also a very different pattern of parental influence on graduation outcomes. Therefore, it is essential to explore and understand the impact of family environment of postgraduates (youth) which is responsible for their mental health growth and development.

MENTAL HEALTH

Mental health is an important determinant of one's integrated personality and balanced behavior identified on the basis of the level of his/her adjustment to own self, others and family environment (Paresh B. Acharya, 215). Mental health is a crucial aspect of overall well being, and it is particularly important for students (Alysia Marshall-Seslar, 2023). The pressures of academic life, social expectations, and the challenges of transitioning to adulthood can take a significant toll on mental health (Tahsin Kabir, et al., 2024). Thus, students who struggle with mental health issues may find it difficult to succeed academically and may struggle with relationships, making it essential to prioritise mental health in their lives. Therefore, mental health is a crucial aspect of overall well-being for students, especially in their postgraduate education.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Georgia Barbayannis, etal. (2022) studied on academic stress and mental well-being of college students. The study observed academic stress may be the single most dominant stress factor that affects the mental well-being of college students, and academic stress in college is also significantly correlated to psychological well-being in the students. Xiaoyi Jin, et al. (2022) studied the impact of family factors on children's mental health during home quarantine with a aim to analyze the factors affecting children's mental health during home quarantine from the perspective of family composition. The study found that family factors, especially the parent-child interaction, played an important role in the mental health of children during the epidemic. Zixiang Luo, etal. (2022) studied on family environment and college students' psychological health, and observed that family environment is a subjective factor to determine mental health of college students. Amela Salihovic etal. (2021) studied on the connection between the family environment and the mental health of individuals, where they found that depressive symptoms in parents is one of the main risk factors for the development of depressive symptoms in children, especially in the age of adulthood and close emotional relationships with parents result in positive psychological outcomes for children. Thus, the family environment has a very significant role and impact on the mental health of the children. Brae Anne McArthur et.al, (2021) studied on family factors associated with child mental health and well-being, and found that family factors are closely associated with the mental health and well-being of the children, especially in their adolescent age-groups. Eduarda Souza Dilleggi etal. (2021) studied on associations between family environment resources and mental health problems in children. In this study the authors used descriptive and correlation analysis and found that the more the mental health problems were present in children with the lower the family resources offer. Swikruti Behera etal. (2021) studied on mental health status of students pursuing professional training. The study revealed that male students were found to have higher prevalence of mental abnormalities and a significant higher prevalence of depression is seen in day-scholars compared to hostellers. Nursing students are having significantly higher prevalence of depression and non-psychotic mental illness as compared to dental, engineering, and medical students. Medical students are having the lowest rate of depression than other nonmedical professional subjects.

The mental health of college students with reference to their family environment, Bina Makvana (2020) found that mental health for family environment of the boys and girls students were significant. The students who experience poor parental environment have consistently greater distress than their non-exposed counterparts throughout adulthood.

The association of family structure with health behavior, mental health, and perceived academic achievement of students at their adolescent age Hanul Park and Kang-Sook Lee (2020) found that non-intact families had significantly higher odds of smoking a cigarette, drinking a sip of alcohol, internet use, physical activity, and sexual experience, and mental health issues such as depression, suicidal ideation, perceived stress, and poor perceived health status of students than intact families (two-parent families), and also non-intact families were significantly related to low perceived academic achievement compared to intact ones. Usman and Izhari (2020) studied on effect of family environment, peers, self-control and financial literacy on consumptive behavior of students. The results show that self control has a positive effect on student consumptive behavior, where the higher a person's self control, the lower the consumptive behavior. Whereas, family environment, peer, and financial literacy variables have a negative influence on consumptive behavior. Bhupendra Singh & Mithilesh Kumar Yadav (2019) studied on family environment and mental health of adolescents. Since, the adolescents need careful attention from their parents, teachers and other members in the society for their proper development and welfare, parents in all cultures and societies struggle to make the right decisions in bringing up their children. During their college studied adolescents want to raise human beings to enjoy life, think well of themselves, and develop capacities to fulfill their goals and get along successfully when they grow up. But parents want their children to learn to live harmoniously with other people and to form and maintain close, constructive relationships. Thus, dimensions of family and school environment and gender as significant variable in affecting mental health of adolescents.

In addition to the above literature Tripathy & Sahu (2019) studied on impact of family environment on socio-emotional adjustment of adolescent girls in rural areas. The purpose of this study was to assess the effect of the adolescent girls' family environment and their socio-emotional adjustment. The analysis of this study revealed that all the eight family environment factors, i.e. cohesion, expressiveness conflict, acceptance and caring, independence, active-recreational orientation, organization and control together showed significant role in socio-emotional and educational adjustment of adolescent girls. Rajesh Kumar Beenu Varma (2019) studied on effect of family environment on physical and psychological health among adolescents. The study observed that family environment and role played by each family member and family process provide a network of social, physical, and intellectual forces, which affect the adolescents learning, mental peace, thought content, physical health and thinking process. The results depict that there was significant gender differences on physical health among adolescents and gender differences on general health of the adolescents. The results also showed that there was significant relationship between family environment and health among adolescents. Neerja Shukla (2018) studied on effect of family environment on mental health of nursing students. The findings of this study show a significant relationship was established between underlying sets of family relationship and personal growth dimensions with mental health. Harsha P.P. (2017) studied on family environment and academic stress as predictors of depression in adolescents. It is observed that academic matters are the most important sources of chronic stress in young people and have significant associations with mental health problems, such as depression, anxiety and suicidal ideation. There is an increasing concern regarding study pressure and its relationships with mental health problems among adolescents.

Moreover, many studies have been reviewed on the impact of family environment on the mental health of children, adolescents and college students with reference to their academic achievement, behavioural attitude and psychological well-being, but there is no particular study on the impact of family environment on the mental health of postgraduate students. Therefore, this study has selected by the researcher for investigation.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

While most of the research on mental health was done on children and adolescents, either their symptoms were attributed to physical illness rather than the psychological consideration with increasing number of adolescents attempting suicide and leaving their home early it become important to conduct a study on impact of family environment on mental health of students, especially the postgraduates. It will also help them to understand the role of family environment and mental health status of students. The present study is a attempt to see the relationship of family environment with mental health of postgraduates and how the different dimension of family environment influence them and their mental health.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

In recent times, youth confront enormous problems because they deviate their attention towards virtual reality and have gone far away from the reality of life. In this situation family environment provides a social and moral training within the family and plays crucial part in one's development and formation of behaviour. According to Gottman (2001), parents are the coaches of their children's emotions and they contribute to the understanding and recognition of negative effects, the development of the child's sense of control and optimism or in the effective regulation of emotions. Healthy family environment facilitates insight and development among youth. Young individuals enhance their experience by utilizing their knowledge of esteem, consideration, unity, concurrence, affable and changeability while interacting with home conventions and family relationships (Galvin et al., 2015). Earlier studies also found that the youngsters growing up in families with a happy, harmonious parental marriage, experience a fewer problems and higher wellbeing (Spruijt and De Goede 1997). Naik and Shukla (2018) opined that "family environment had a significant role in making the person socially adjustable and emotionally stable. Therefore, family is the center of social, emotional, moral education and values, which influence on the mental health of students, especially in post-graduation level. A disciplined, calm, peaceful environment of any family helps in developing proper emotions and social skills of their children which in turn helps them in adjusting with different situations and focusing their goal and on their performance. Hence it is important to examine the influence of family environment on mental health of postgraduates.

Objectives

1. To study the family environment of the postgraduate students.
2. To examine the mental health status of the postgraduate students.
3. To examine the relationship between family environment and mental health of postgraduate students.
4. To study the impact of family environment on the mental health status of postgraduate students

Hypotheses

1. Thereis no significant difference on family environment of the postgraduate students
2. Mental health score of PostGraduate Students does not differ significantly.
3. Thereis no significant relationship between family environment and mental health of postgraduate students.
4. The mental health status of postgraduate students does not determined by their family environment.

Research Methodology

A descriptive, cross-sectional study design was used to assess the family environment and mental health of conveniently selected 60 postgraduate students of both boys and girls between the age-group 21-25 years in selected colleges and universities of Hyderabad. The sample size of 60 PG students was estimated using quota sampling. Hence, a quota sampling methodology was followed in data collection from a homogeneous group. It involves a two-step process where three variables can be used to gather information from the population.

Tools used

Socio-demographic data sheet

It is a self-administered tool prepared by the investigator and used to measure the socio-demographic profile of participants. It consists of six items which are gender, age, field of study, family status, living status and area of residence. The total administration time for this tool was approximately 3–5 min. Content validity of the tool is determined by expert in the field of psychiatry, psychology, and academic respectively.

Family Environment Scale

The family environment scale was developed by Moos (1974), which has been adopted and used in this study. This scale consists of three dimensions which are: Relationship dimensions, Personal Growth dimensions and System Maintenance dimensions. All these three dimensions contain 69 statements. The first one is Relationship dimensions, which contains of 4 sub-dimensions, i.e. Cohesion, Expressiveness, Conflict and Acceptance and caring. The second one is Personal Growth Dimensions, which contains 2 sub-dimensions such as Independence and Active Recreational Orientation. The third one is System Maintenance Dimensions, which contains 2 sub-dimensions such as Organisation and Control. Hence, the total tool contains 69 statements of 3 dimensions, among which 41 statements are positive and 28 are negative. Thus the respondents were requested to respond to the items by marking any one of the five alternative response options i.e. Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree and Strongly Disagree, which were scored as 5,4,3,2 and 1 for positive statements and 1,2,3,4 and 5 for negative statements.

Mental Health Inventory

The Mental Health Inventory (MHI) is widely-accepted for study the mental health status of subjects of investigation. This tool was developed by Veit and Ware (1983), which covers a wide range of negative and positive emotions. This tool contains 18 items. In this MHI there are 4 subscales, such as Anxiety, Depression, Behavioral Control, and Positive Affect. Each subscale contains with number of items of both positive and negative statements. Most of these items are self-explanatory and should be responded by objective type responses like All of the time (1), Most of the time (2), A good bit of the time (3), Some of the time (4), A little of the time (5), and None of the time (6). Based on the responses the score value will be calculated for each statement.

After data was collected from the respondents descriptive statistics were used and data analysis. The statistics techniques like frequencies and percentage analysis, cross-distribution analysed were done to find out the relationship of variables, regression analysis were done to find out the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. Hence, the percentage test, chi-square test and regression test were used in this study.

Data Analysis

The demographic features of the students in the study are analyzed in terms of gender, age, subjects in which they are studying, family status, living status and residential area of post graduate students. The frequency distribution and percentage of the demographic features of the students are presented in the following Table-1. Thus, the following table illustrates the demographic features of the students surveyed in the current study.

Table-1: Demographic details of the sample respondents

Category	Variables	Frequency (N=60)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	23	38.3
	Female	37	61.7
Age (in years)	Below 21	3	5.0
	21-25	46	76.7
	26-30	7	11.7
	31 and above	4	6.6
Field of study	Arts and social science	14	23.3
	Commerce	14	23.3
	Management Studies	16	26.7
	Science	16	26.7
Family Status	High	2	3.3
	Average	49	81.7
	Low	9	15.0
Living Status	City	39	65.0
	Town	21	35.0
Area	Rural	20	33.3
	Urban	40	66.7

The sample comprised 39.1% male and 60.9% female students, among which 5.0% are the age range below 21 years, 76.7% are in 21-25, 11.7% are in 26-30 and 6.6% are in above 31 years. According to field of study, Arts and Social Science at 23.3%, Commerce at 23.3%, Management studies at 26.7% and Science department at 26.7%. Regarding to Family Status of students, 3.3% have belong to high status, 81.7% have average status and 15.% have low status. As regard to living status of students 65.0% where living status of city students and 35.0%. where from the town students. Majority of the where from the urban area 66.7% as 33.3% where from rural area.

Table-2: Family Environment of postgraduate students

Family Environment Inventory	High	Average	Low	Total
Cohesion	5 (8.3)	40 (66.7)	15 (25.0)	60 (100.0)
Expressiveness	5 (8.3)	39 (65.0)	16 (26.7)	60 (100.0)
Acceptance and Caring	2 (3.3)	35 (58.4)	23 (38.3)	60 (100.0)
Independence	1 (1.6)	25 (41.7)	34 (56.7)	60 (100.0)
Active-Recreational Orientation	10 (16.7)	36 (60.0)	14 (23.3)	60 (100.0)
Organization	12 (20.0)	34 (56.7)	14 (23.3)	60 (100.0)
Control	10 (16.7)	32 (53.3)	18 (30.0)	60 (100.0)

In the Family Environment Inventory (FEI) the total score of each dimension was divided in to 3 groups according to the perceptual score of the respondents. The respondents who obtained the score of 1 or 2 considered as mild, who obtained the score of 3 considered as moderate and who obtained the score of 4 or 5 considered as high level of that particular dimension. This tool is used in this study to estimate the family environment condition of the postgraduate students. In this context the Table-2 represents the family environment inventory dimensions and their level of representation among the postgraduate students in the study areas. According to the table it shows that the cohesion of postgraduate students was found high among 8.3 percent, average among 66.7 percent and low among 25.0 percent. Regarding to expressiveness of the postgraduate students on family environment data reveals that high among 8.3 percent, average among 65.0 percent and low among 26.7%.

Regarding dimension of acceptance and caring of the postgraduate students from their family indicates that 3.3 percent have high, 58.4 percent have average and 38.3% have low acceptance and caring. Independence of postgraduate students in the family environment the data infers that 1.6 percent found high, 41.7 percent found average and 56.7 percent found low independence. Regarding to active-recreational orientation of postgraduate students shows that 16.7 percent are with high, 60.0 percent are with average and 23.3 percent are with low, active-recreational orientation in their family environment. The organization aspect of family environment of the postgraduate students the data revealed that 20.0 percent are found high, 56.7 percent are found average and 23.3 percent are found low organization, with reference to control in the family environment of postgraduate students the data shows that 16.7 percent are having high, 53.3 percent are having average and 30.0 percent are having low control of family environment.

Table-3: Mental Health status of postgraduate students

Mental Health Inventory	Mild	Moderate	High	Total
Anxiety	5 (8.3)	45 (75.0)	10 (16.7)	60 (100.0)
Depression	3 (5.0)	41 (68.3)	16 (26.7)	60 (100.0)
Behavior Control	1 (1.7)	36 (60.0)	23 (38.3)	60 (100.0)
Positive Effect	1 (1.7)	32 (53.3)	27 (45.0)	60 (100.0)
Mental Health (Total)	1 (1.7)	47 (78.3)	12 (20.0)	60 (100.0)

In the Mental Health Inventory (MHI) the total score of each dimension has divided in to 3 groups according to the perceptual scores of the respondents. The respondents who secured the score of 1 or 2 considered as mild, who secured the score of 3 or 4 considered as moderate and who secured the score of 5 or 6 considered as high level of that particular dimension. This tool is used in this study to estimate the level of mental health status of the postgraduate students. In this regard the Table-3 the anxiety level of post graduate students revealed that as many as 75.0 percent are in moderate level, and from the rest 16.7 percent are with high level and the remaining 8.3 percent are with a mild level of anxiety. As regard to depression among postgraduate students it is found that a major group of 68.3 percent are with moderate level of depression, remaining 26.7 percent are high level of depression and a minimum of 5.0 percent are with mild level of depression. Regarding behavioural control of postgraduate students it is observed that the maximum group of 60.0 percent is with moderate level of behavioural control, and from the rest 38.3 percent are found high level and a low level of 1.7 percent are with mild level of behavioural control. As regard to positive affect postgraduate students the data reveals that 53.3 percent are with moderate level positive effect followed by high level among 45.0 percent and average number of students 1.7 percent are with mild level of positive effect of mental health. Hence the overall mental health status among postgraduate students the data shows that as many as 78.3 percent are with moderate level, and from the rest 20.0 percent are with high level and the remaining 1.7 percent are with a mild level of mental health status.

Table-4: Relationship between family environment and mental health status of postgraduate students

Family Environment Conflict	Mental Health status			Total
	Mild	Moderate	High	
Low Conflict	-	1 (1.7)	-	1 (1.7)
Average Conflict	1 (1.7)	23 (38.3)	9 (15.0)	33 (55.0)
High Conflict	1 (1.7)	19 (31.7)	6 (10.0)	26 (43.3)
Total	2 (3.3)	43 (71.7)	15 (25.0)	60 (100.0)
Chi square - 19.70**, df:4, T- value:13.3				

**significant at 1% level

The table 4 shows the relationship between family environment and mental health of postgraduate students. According to the distribution of family environment conflicts and mental health status of postgraduate students it is found that out of total low family environment conflict (1.7%), found moderate level of mental health problem. Among total average family environment conflict members as many as 38.3 percent are found moderate level followed by 15.0 percent with high level of mental health problem, and only one person i.e. 1.7 percent found mild level of mental health. Whereas, from the total high level family environment conflict persons a dominated group of 31.7 percent observed moderate level of mental health, and from the rest 10.0 percent are found high level and 1.7 percent found mild level of mental health. To find the impact of family environment conflicts of postgraduate students on their mental health status the chi-square test has been applied on the distribution of these two variables, where the calculated chi-square value 19.70 indicate significant at 1% level because the df is 4 and the table value is 13.3. This infers that there is an impact of family environment on the mental status of the postgraduate students, where family environment conflicts found more or high there will be high level of mental health problems.

Regression Analysis Model

In this model of regression the researcher estimated the impact of family environment on mental health of postgraduate students, where family environment was taken as independent variable and mental health of postgraduate students was taken as dependent variable.

Total number of respondents in the selected area (N=60)

Multiple Regression Model $Y=a+x_1b_1+x_2b_2+x_3b_3+x_4b_4+x_5b_5+ \dots\dots\dots$

Dependent Variable: Y = Mental Health of postgraduate students

Independent Variables:

- x₁ ->Cohesion – Degree of commitment, help and support family members provided for one another
- x₂ -> Expressiveness – Extent to which family members are encouraged to act openly and express their feelings and thoughts directly
- x₃ ->Conflict – Amount of openly expressed aggression and conflict among family members
- x₄ ->Acceptance and Caring – Extent to which the members are unconditionally accepted and the degree to which caring is expressed in the family
- x₅ ->Independence – Extent to which family members are assertive and independently make their own decisions
- x₆ ->Active-Recreational Orientation – Extent of participation in Social and recreational activities
- x₇ ->Organization – Degree of importance of clear organization structure in planning family activities and responsibilities
- x₈ ->Control – Degree of limit setting within a family

Table-5: Impact of Family Environment on Mental Health of the Postgraduate Students

Regression Summary for Dependent Variable: Mental Health						
R= 0.8295 R ² = 0.6881 Adjusted R ² = 0.6763						
F(8,211)=58.201 p<0.0000 Std. Error of estimate: 0.2434						
Family Environment variables	Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t(51)	p-level
Intercept			0.83	0.10	8.60	0.00
Cohesion	0.43	0.17	0.33	0.13	2.54*	0.01
Expressiveness	0.03	0.18	0.03	0.13	0.19	0.85
Conflict	0.25	0.09	0.20	0.08	2.66*	0.01
Acceptance and Caring	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.08	0.92	0.36
Independence	0.16	0.06	0.14	0.05	2.63*	0.01
Active-Recreational Orientation	0.55	0.18	0.37	0.12	3.08**	0.00
Organization	0.16	0.16	0.11	0.10	1.03	0.30
Control	0.51	0.11	0.33	0.07	4.50**	0.00

* Significant at 5% level; ** Significant at 1% level

In this model of linear multiple regressions found best fit to measure the influence of family environment dimensions on mental health of post graduate students. This is because the F-value in this regression is 58.201 which is satisfactorily significant at 1% level because the p-value is less than 0.00. This model also explains R² at 67.63% of variation.

In this model of regression analysis out of the total 8 explanatory variables of family environment as many as 5 variables are found to be significant, but three variables i.e. Expressiveness, Acceptance and caring and Organisation are not indicate any significance. Thus, the significant variables are Cohesion, Conflict, Independence, Active-recreational orientation and Control. Among these significant variables Cohesion, Conflict and Independence are showing 5% significance and Active-recreational orientation and Control variables are indicating 1% significance. This infers that where there is more score of these independent variables there will be more mental health problems among postgraduate students. For example, where the conflicts in the family environment are more and the family control is high among the post graduate students, there the mental health problems are more.

CONCLUSION

The family environment plays a crucial role in shaping the psychological well-being and mental health of college students, especially in their age at post graduation study. Positive family environment, such as cohesion, open communication, and emotional support, can contribute to better mental health outcomes, while negative dynamics, such as conflict, neglect, and lack of support, can lead to psychological disturbances such as anxiety, depression, and stress. Understanding and addressing these factors is essential for promoting overall well-being and academic success of postgraduate students. Thus, the study revealed that there is a positive association found between good family environment and low scores on stress, anxiety and depression of postgraduate students. Therefore, it could be concluded that enhancing positive family relationships may improve student mental health. Dysfunctional families relate to poorer adjustment. Fostering healthy family environments could have enduring benefits for postgraduate students' psychological well-being, which reflects on their mental health.

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